

Ajax Analytics

Method Summary

Estimating High-Resolution VOC
Concentrations from PID Sensor Signals
and Triggered Canister Sample Results

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1. OVERVIEW AND KEY PREMISES

When measuring air pollutants, the overarching vision would be to know exactly what gaseous compounds are in the air, in every cubic meter of space, during every second of every day, around the world. Of course, achieving this goal is infeasible due to technology and resource limitations. Therefore, every scientist studying the sources and impact of air pollution is forced to compromise their measurement approach and increase their level of assumption, or modeling, in order to achieve enough of the overarching vision as needed in order to serve the specific research objective of their study.

Measuring volatile organic compounds (VOC) in ambient air has historically been a challenge for researchers and industry due to the expensive and time-consuming nature of available technologies. The primary ambient measurement technologies for VOCs that have been in use since the mid-20th century have been whole air samples and gas chromatography equipment, both of which provide highly accurate concentration measurements for individual VOCs at the time of the sample.

The major challenges with these technologies are the high cost per sample. Whole air samples can cost between \$200 and \$700 per sample after costs of sampling equipment, labor to deploy and collect the sample, and costs of lab equipment and labor to analyze the whole air sample to deliver concentrations for the VOC analytes. Field gas chromatography (GC) equipment typically requires an air-conditioned shelter to house the equipment. Costs for a trailer-based GC VOC monitoring station can be between \$100,000 and \$400,000 to deploy initially, with \$60,000 to \$200,000 in annual ongoing maintenance costs incorporating labor, calibration gases, power costs, and equipment maintenance and repair.

Because of the high cost per sample for VOC measurements, measurements have historically been compromised either in spatial coverage, time/resolution coverage, or in duration of monitoring. These compromises are especially limiting when measuring VOCs, as many VOCs have a short lifespan in ambient air, often reacting with other compounds such as NO_x and sunlight to create ozone many miles away from the initial emission and within hours or days of the initial VOC emission.

Small VOC sensors using photo-ionization detector (PID) technology have provided additional capability to monitor ambient VOCs. These small sensors can be solar and battery powered, are inexpensive enough to allow for wide spatial networks, and provide time resolution on a scale of seconds to minutes. The downside of PID sensors is that they react to over 900 VOCs without providing information about which VOCs are in the sampled air. The second limitation of PID sensors is that certain VOCs will create a larger signal response in the sensor. This means that the composition of VOCs in the ambient air will greatly affect the magnitude of the signal response from the sensor.

PID sensors bolster time and space resolution for measurements.

The mix of VOCs in the air can make a big difference in the size of the sensor's response.

PID sensors can auto-trigger whole air canister samples, providing key information about the mix of VOCs in the air during an emissions plume event.

Recent technological advances have paired PID sensors with whole air canister samples using a concept called “triggered sampling”. These technologies connect whole air canister samples with a PID sensor system. When the PID sensor identifies an emission event, or an elevated level of VOCs in the ambient air, the system will automatically open a valve and collect a whole air sample. After lab analysis, this whole air sample provides accurate information about the composition mix and concentration of VOCs in the air during the whole air canister sample period, which may be from a few seconds to an hour in duration.

In our work at Ajax Analytics, we have collected over 300 triggered canister samples with VOC concentrations ranging from just above normal background to measured concentrations over 320 times normal background levels.

The figure to the right shows a box-and-whisker distribution of the sum of 49 volatile organic compounds (known as Total VOC, or TVOC) from 1,981 week-long duration VOC canister samples on the left, and the distribution of 183 15-second triggered canister samples on the right. Take note of the concentration differences between a 7-day integrated sample and a short, 15-second triggered sample. From our observations so far, a 15-second sample can present up to 320 times the VOC concentrations of a 7-day sample, highlighting the incredibly transient nature of VOC concentrations in ambient air.

The incredibly transient nature of VOCs in ambient air, coupled with our lacking ability to measure VOCs in every cubic meter of space during every second of every day, means that we needed to develop a model that can estimate specific VOC concentrations during high-resolution time periods when we do not have a speciated sample concentration.

This paper identifies a method for using PID sensor signals to estimate VOC concentrations during periods when the composition of the air mass is known with high certainty. This modeling ability extends the ability of PID sensors and triggered canisters to provide VOC concentrations across more time and space than measurement provides alone, while also providing estimates for potential human exposures to VOC concentrations.

320x difference between TVOC_CSU49 maximum readings at 1-week and 15-second sample resolution
113x difference in TVOC_CSU49 means

2. ESTIMATION METHOD

2.1 Desired Method Output

The desired outputs of this modeling method are high-time resolution concentration estimates of individual compounds at the measurement site before, during, and after a plume event.

Effectively, we want to output a table of measured VOC compounds with minute-by-minute concentration estimates that were likely experienced at the site where the measurements were taken.

2.2 Method Inputs

This estimating method requires:

1. A high-time resolution PID sensor signal.
 - a. The units of the PID measurement are inconsequential, but the precision of the measurement should be high. If the PID output units are mV, then the precision should be to the tenths place (0,000.0). If the PID output units are “ppm as isobutylene” then the precision should be to the hundredths place (or thousandths if possible) (0.00 or 0.000).
 - b. Time resolution should be at least a 1-minute PID averaging interval. 10-second or 15-second PID averaging intervals are better and will very likely improve the estimate accuracy.
2. Knowledge of the VOC compositions of the measured air mass before, during, and after a plume event.
 - a. VOC composition information is best provided by whole air canister samples at the site during normal baseline conditions and during the plume event (via triggered canister).
 - b. Normal baseline VOC composition and concentrations can be assumed based on regional background measurements with little impact to the model’s output.
 - c. VOC composition mix and concentrations during the plume event must be measured concentrations during the plume event, as any inaccuracy can have a material impact on the estimating model output.

2.3 VOC Estimation Method

The estimating method relies on the assumption that the mix of actual VOCs in the plume are constant throughout the plume window.

We will use the PID signal to the right as an example. We assume that during the period prior to 22:39, the PID was measuring VOCs in ambient background air. During the spike in the PID signal, we assume that the PID was measuring a special “plume composition” of VOCs – which we were able to capture and measure in a 1-minute triggered whole air canister at 22:40. After the event is over (i.e.: the plume stopped or was shifted by the wind in another direction), we assume that the PID was again measuring VOCs in ambient background air.

2.3.1 Prepare Conversion Factors

To create minute-by-minute VOC concentration estimates from a 1-minute PID signal and a 1-minute canister sample, one needs to calculate the following conversion factors.

Note: These examples use benzene as the VOC being estimated and use a 1-minute sample resolution. However, any PID-measured VOC can be estimated. Results will become more accurate with A) higher measurement time-resolutions and B) alignment between PID signal time-averaging and the duration of whole-air-sample collection.

Plume Event Benzene/PID Conversion Factor

This conversion factor is calculated by taking the benzene concentration from the triggered sample and dividing by the average PID signal for the duration of the triggered sample.

Plume Event Benzene/PID Conversion Factor

=

1-minute benzene at time of sample / 1-minute average PID signal during the triggered canister sample

From our example, we measured benzene in the triggered whole air sample canister at 93.381 ppb. The average 1-minute PID signal while the whole air sample was being collected was 333.7 mV. These measurements give us a **Plume Event Benzene/PID Conversion Factor** of **0.280**.

Ambient Benzene/PID Conversion Factor

This conversion factor is calculated by taking the ambient benzene concentration (ideally from a recent baseline/background sample at the monitoring site) and dividing by the baseline PID signal (i.e.: the PID signal during times when the PID was measuring 'clean' background air).

Ambient Benzene/PID Conversion Factor

=

background benzene around time of sample / minimum PID signal from 1 day window prior to the plume event

From our example, we measured benzene during a 7-day sample at a nearby site during the same week at 0.073 ppb. We will use this benzene concentration as our baseline 'clean air' measurement. The minimum PID signal from the hours before the plume event was 93.5 mV. We use this PID signal as our baseline 'clean air' PID signal measurement. These measurements give us an **Ambient Benzene/PID Conversion Factor** of **0.00078**.

2.3.2 Apply Conversion Factors

The estimation is performed for each PID measurement window for a period before, during, and after the observed plume event. In our example, our objective is to calculate a 1-hour average benzene concentration during the event at the location of the measurements. Therefore, we will choose to calculate a benzene estimate for each minute for a period of 60 minutes before and 60 minutes after the triggered sample.

We apply the Plume Event Conversion Factor during the periods/minutes with elevated PID measurements (while the PID sensor was measuring the plume composition) and we apply the Ambient Event Conversion Factor during the periods/minutes without elevated PID measurements (while the PID was measuring the background air composition).

The selection of which periods to apply each conversion factor can be done manually every time the model is run. A more consistent application requires developing calculated rules for when to apply the Ambient Conversion Factor and when to apply the Plume Event Conversion Factor. Ajax Analytics is developing and testing different methods for automatically applying conversion factors based on algorithms that identify when the plume event started and stopped.

VOC Concentration Estimate

The VOC Concentration Estimate (the Benzene Estimate in our example) is then calculated for each minute as:

$$\text{Benzene Estimate} = \text{PID Signal} * \text{Conversion Factor}$$

The table below shows an excerpt of the full calculated matrix:

Start Time	End Time	PID Signal Output	Ambient or Plume Event Conversion Factor	Benzene Estimate
7/13/22 22:34:01	7/13/22 22:35:00	94.0	0.00078	0.07
7/13/22 22:35:01	7/13/22 22:36:00	94.0	0.00078	0.07
7/13/22 22:36:01	7/13/22 22:37:00	94.0	0.00078	0.07
7/13/22 22:37:01	7/13/22 22:38:00	94.1	0.00078	0.07
7/13/22 22:38:01	7/13/22 22:39:00	94.1	0.00078	0.07
7/13/22 22:39:01	7/13/22 22:40:00	149.5	0.280	41.83
7/13/22 22:40:01	7/13/22 22:41:00	333.7	0.280	93.38
7/13/22 22:41:01	7/13/22 22:42:00	336.0	0.280	94.03
7/13/22 22:42:01	7/13/22 22:43:00	168.2	0.280	47.07
7/13/22 22:43:01	7/13/22 22:44:00	126.9	0.280	35.50
7/13/22 22:44:01	7/13/22 22:45:00	136.4	0.280	38.17
7/13/22 22:45:01	7/13/22 22:46:00	130.0	0.280	36.37
7/13/22 22:46:01	7/13/22 22:47:00	109.2	0.280	30.57
7/13/22 22:47:01	7/13/22 22:48:00	103.1	0.280	28.85
7/13/22 22:48:01	7/13/22 22:49:00	100.9	0.280	28.24
7/13/22 22:49:01	7/13/22 22:50:00	99.7	0.00078	0.08
7/13/22 22:50:01	7/13/22 22:51:00	98.9	0.00078	0.08
7/13/22 22:51:01	7/13/22 22:52:00	98.3	0.00078	0.08
7/13/22 22:52:01	7/13/22 22:53:00	97.9	0.00078	0.08
7/13/22 22:53:01	7/13/22 22:54:00	97.7	0.00078	0.08
7/13/22 22:54:01	7/13/22 22:55:00	97.5	0.00078	0.08
7/13/22 22:55:01	7/13/22 22:56:00	97.2	0.00078	0.08
7/13/22 22:56:01	7/13/22 22:57:00	97.0	0.00078	0.08
7/13/22 22:57:01	7/13/22 22:58:00	96.9	0.00078	0.08
7/13/22 22:58:01	7/13/22 22:59:00	96.8	0.00078	0.08
7/13/22 22:59:01	7/13/22 23:00:00	96.7	0.00078	0.08

2.3.3 Calculate Longer Term Averages

In Ajax Analytics' most common usage of this method, we calculate 1-hour average estimates for individual VOCs to provide context in relation to acute health guideline values, which often require a minimum 1-hour exposure duration.

To calculate longer-term averages, one simply adds up the Benzene Estimates from the minutes during the desired longer-term average duration and divides by the number of minutes included. In our case, we want to find the potential maximum 1-hour exposure from the plume event at the monitoring site.

We calculate a 60-minute moving average (-30, +30 moving average) for each minute of the estimating window. The maximum of this moving average provides the 1-hour benzene estimate that was our objective when using this method, in this case a **1-Hour Benzene Estimate** of **7.96 ppb**, based on the minute-by-minute PID signal and the 93.381 ppb measurement of benzene from the 1-minute canister sample.

The table below shows an excerpt of the 1-hour moving average applied to the Benzene Estimate:

Start Time	End Time	PID Signal Output	Ambient or Plume Event Conversion Factor	Benzene Estimate	1-hour Benzene Moving Average
7/13/22 22:34:01	7/13/22 22:35:00	94.0	0.00078	0.07	7.96
7/13/22 22:35:01	7/13/22 22:36:00	94.0	0.00078	0.07	7.96
7/13/22 22:36:01	7/13/22 22:37:00	94.0	0.00078	0.07	7.96
7/13/22 22:37:01	7/13/22 22:38:00	94.1	0.00078	0.07	7.96
7/13/22 22:38:01	7/13/22 22:39:00	94.1	0.00078	0.07	7.96
7/13/22 22:39:01	7/13/22 22:40:00	149.5	0.280	41.83	7.96
7/13/22 22:40:01	7/13/22 22:41:00	333.7	0.280	93.38	7.96
7/13/22 22:41:01	7/13/22 22:42:00	336.0	0.280	94.03	7.96
7/13/22 22:42:01	7/13/22 22:43:00	168.2	0.280	47.07	7.96
7/13/22 22:43:01	7/13/22 22:44:00	126.9	0.280	35.50	7.96
7/13/22 22:44:01	7/13/22 22:45:00	136.4	0.280	38.17	7.96
7/13/22 22:45:01	7/13/22 22:46:00	130.0	0.280	36.37	7.96
7/13/22 22:46:01	7/13/22 22:47:00	109.2	0.280	30.57	7.96
7/13/22 22:47:01	7/13/22 22:48:00	103.1	0.280	28.85	7.96
7/13/22 22:48:01	7/13/22 22:49:00	100.9	0.280	28.24	7.96
7/13/22 22:49:01	7/13/22 22:50:00	99.7	0.00078	0.08	7.96
7/13/22 22:50:01	7/13/22 22:51:00	98.9	0.00078	0.08	7.96
7/13/22 22:51:01	7/13/22 22:52:00	98.3	0.00078	0.08	7.96
7/13/22 22:52:01	7/13/22 22:53:00	97.9	0.00078	0.08	7.96
7/13/22 22:53:01	7/13/22 22:54:00	97.7	0.00078	0.08	7.96
7/13/22 22:54:01	7/13/22 22:55:00	97.5	0.00078	0.08	7.96
7/13/22 22:55:01	7/13/22 22:56:00	97.2	0.00078	0.08	7.96
7/13/22 22:56:01	7/13/22 22:57:00	97.0	0.00078	0.08	7.96
7/13/22 22:57:01	7/13/22 22:58:00	96.9	0.00078	0.08	7.96
7/13/22 22:58:01	7/13/22 22:59:00	96.8	0.00078	0.08	7.96
7/13/22 22:59:01	7/13/22 23:00:00	96.7	0.00078	0.08	7.96

3. CONCLUSION

Two of the most important things to keep in mind when applying this method for VOC concentration estimates are:

- 1) The PID signal responds differently to different air compositions.
 - a. A PID signal of 500 mV (or 2.3 ppb as isobutylene) in one plume circumstance may not reflect the same individual VOC concentrations as a PID signal of 500 mV (or 2.3 ppb as isobutylene) in a different plume circumstance. It is Ajax Analytics' opinion that the scientific community does not have enough data or vetted analysis to assume plume compositions based on nearby emission sources, therefore this model should only be applied when the plume composition can be reasonably assured, ideally though triggered whole air sample results.
- 2) Time resolution, more specifically time aggregation, can make a highly significant difference in the PID signal and canister sample results, therefore tangibly changing the Conversion Factors, therefore reducing confidence in the VOC Estimates.
 - a. Ambient VOCs are not normally (Gaussian) distributed and present incredibly wide variability in concentrations. Therefore, time aggregation from seconds to minutes can change a mean calculation by a factor of tens, and time aggregation from minutes to weeks can change a mean calculation by a factor of hundreds.

This method should only be applied when PID signal time averaging is aligned with, or very close to, the triggered whole air canister sample duration. As with all models, the results are subject to the quality of the inputs and the model should be tested and validated. At this time, Ajax Analytics has tested this estimating model by co-locating triggered samples with time-duration offsets. Thus far, we have found excellent alignment between the estimated VOC concentrations using this method and the actual VOC concentrations measured in co-located, longer-duration triggered canister samples.

This document defines the September 2022 draft of the Ajax Analytics VOC Concentration Estimating Model using PID Signal with Whole Air Canister Sample Concentrations. This method is undergoing further testing and development and should be considered in a draft format. Though the method is actively used at this time, ongoing improvements may change some or all of the Ajax Analytics method in the future. Specifically, the anticipated weaknesses of this model occur during the gradient mixing of the VOC composition toward the edges of the plume event window. As a plume crosses over a site, the site will experience mostly background composition at the edges of the VOC spike and mostly plume composition near the peak of the VOC spike with a composition mixing in between the two that will be dependent upon wind conditions. The next steps in model maturity will be to determine whether addressing this potential gradation improves the model with enough significance to justify the added complexity.